

The Evolution of Electoral Representation and Internal Conflicts in Lebanon

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This intervention explores the impact of Lebanon's confessional representation system on its internal conflicts and electoral system. It traces the historical development of this system, which assigns political seats according to religious groups, from its origin in the 19th century to the present day. It analyzes how each conflict and resolution affected the electoral system and the power-sharing arrangement among different communities. It argues that electoral systems in divided societies should not only ensure effective representation but also foster inter-community cooperation and prevent social isolation. It suggests Lebanon's electoral system should reflect its unique social and political characteristics and uphold its consensual democracy.

Lebanon's confessional representation system emerged from conflicts between the Druze and Christians in Mount Lebanon during Ottoman rule. The first official system of confessional representation was established in 1841 after international intervention to end violence (Rabbat 1986, 180). The solution was to divide Mount Lebanon into two regions *qaimaqamyas*, one led by a Christian governor and the other by a Druze governor. However, conflict resumed in 1845 due to dissatisfaction with authority and tax inequality (Njeim 1995, 275-277). The international powers

then recognized six confessions (Sunnah, Druze, Shia, Catholic, Orthodox, and Maronite) and created two administrative councils composed of 12 members representing the six confessions. Although the confessions felt more represented because the system ensured effective representation, it did not foster cooperation or compromise between them, as they voted in isolated confessional electoral colleges. The *moutassarifya* System, established after the 1845 conflict, replaced the *qaimaqamyas* system in Mount Lebanon. Led by a Christian Ottoman Ruler, it featured an administrative council representing the six confessions based on their demographics. Representatives were directly elected by their communities, and religious leaders collaborated with feudal lords to select council members. The administrative council of the *moutassarifya* was the first kind of representative parliament and the first power-sharing system based on confessional representation in Lebanon (Rabbat 1982, 226-230). Although the confessional electoral college prevented vote trading, the system fostered cooperation and compromise because it gave each confession a voice and made them work together in the same council. This system ensured effective representation while promoting unity against Ottoman interference. For sixty years, this arrangement

facilitated peaceful coexistence in Mount Lebanon until 1920.

The first official system of confessional representation emerged in 1920 when Great Lebanon was announced and defined with its final borders. The political system relied on a national pact between Christians and Muslims, who agreed to share power and keep Lebanon neutral from both the Western and Eastern worlds. The system had four features: a confessional quota in parliament for each group based on a 6:5 ratio—6 for the Christians and 5 for the Muslims; a multi-confessional electoral college where voters from different groups voted for all the representatives regardless of their religion; a two-round-majoritarian system in lists—bloc vote system—after the abolition of the delegates' system; and large and multi-confessional districts. This system ensured effective representation of the groups, and any attempt by the French mandate to abolish the confessional representation was rejected (Hakim 2005, 260-266). The bloc vote system also promoted accommodation and cooperation among the groups, as it encouraged moderate speech and candidates who could make compromises and peace deals because candidates needed to attract votes from all confessions, especially in large confessionally heterogeneous districts (Ghanem 1972, 160-161). The system maintained peace and coexistence for 32 years from 1920 to 1952.

However, the system was challenged in 1958, and civil unrest broke out due to internal and external factors. The internal factors were the change of the electoral system by the Christian president Camille Chamoun from the bloc vote system to the first past the post system that isolated the groups in small mono-confessional districts, weakening the effective representation of the Muslim

representatives who lost the elections due to the districting by president Chamoun (Johnson 1985, 118). The external factors were the Christians supporting the Eisenhower Doctrine and opposing the USSR, and the Muslims supporting the Egyptian president Gamal Abdel Nasser and his alliance with the Soviets. The 1958 violent clashes between Christians and Muslims led to the dissolution of the 1957 parliament, the election of a moderate president Fouad Chehab in 1958, the adoption of a new electoral law in 1960, and new parliamentary elections in 1960. The bloc vote system which was reinstated in 26 districts balanced the effective representation of the groups and the cooperation between them. The over-representation of Christians was offset by the influence of Muslim voters in electing 13 Christian MPs out of 54. The confessions were pushed once again to cooperate in the multi-confessional districts. This system led to 15 years of peace and coexistence from 1960 to 1975. The 1960 electoral system was fair and stable for all Lebanese sects (Taqi Al-Din 1996, 140). It allowed them to have a proper representation that matched their demographic distribution. The war disrupted the political harmony that was achieved by this system.

The Lebanese civil war started in 1975. Some of the internal reasons for the war were the Muslims' request for a change in the 6:5 ratio of parliamentary representation that favored the Christians, the Muslims' request for more powers for the Sunni prime minister, and fewer powers for the Christian president. Some of the external reasons were the Palestinian armed forces in Lebanon, the Arab-Israeli disputes, and the Lebanese alignment with different international actors. The war destroyed the political unity that was built over 50 years. The war did not happen because of the flaws in the political system

that respected diversity. The political system could have changed peacefully, if not for the Palestinian-Israeli conflict that weighed on it (Harik 1980, 46-47).

The Ta'if Accords in 1989 that ended the civil war modified the system as follows: equal representation in parliament and cabinet between Christians and Muslims (128 MPs split equally between Christians and Muslims), reduced power of the Christian president, increased power of the Sunni prime minister and the cabinet, and Syrian influence over Lebanese politics and politicians. From 1992 to 2005, the bloc vote system in large districts led to the Christians' boycott of the elections because they could not elect their representatives despite the confessional quota (El-Khazen 2000, 81). The electoral system was imposed by the Syrian occupation to favor loyal representatives. The redistricting in the 2000 electoral law also affected the representation of all Lebanese groups, especially the Sunni community. This resulted in the emergence of national cooperation between Christian, Sunni and Druze, which peaked in the Cedar Revolution in 2005 after the assassination of prime minister Rafic Hariri. After the Syrian troops left Lebanon, Lebanon was divided between two camps: pro and anti-Syria-Iran. The 2005 parliamentary elections produced a more representative parliament, but not to the satisfaction of Christians whose members of parliament were still influenced by Muslim voters. However, the 2005 elections witnessed cooperation between the groups under the bloc vote system, even though the confessional representation was not always effective. From 1990 to 2005, Lebanon experienced 15 years of confessional tension and misrepresentation (Sleiman 2007, 274).

The 2008 mini-civil war, when the 8 March camp led by Hezbollah took over Beirut

and some regions in Mount Lebanon, led to the Doha Agreement that introduced some changes to the power-sharing system. The Shia community was granted an unofficial veto power by controlling 1/3 of the cabinet, the bloc vote system in 26 districts instead of 13 was adopted which gave the Christians influence on 28 seats out of 64 Christian seats (Doha Agreement 2008, provisions two and three). Some of the internal factors of the 2008 clashes were the Shia's demand for veto power in the cabinet and a proportional representation (PR) system in a single district in Lebanon which would favor them because of their demographic size, and the Christians' demand to change the electoral system that was imposed by the Syrians, and which gave them influence on less than 16 seats. External factors are always present in Lebanese politics and have since the 19th century shaped the political system, the divisions of the Lebanese between the pro- and anti-Syria-Iran camps (14 March and 8 March coalitions) were exacerbated during that period. After the 2009 parliamentary elections, the Christians felt more represented, but the Shia continued to demand a full PR system to increase their influence on the seats (Catusse, Karam, and Lamlou 2011, 299). The 2009 parliamentary elections showed some cooperation among the groups, as they needed each other due to the block vote system in mixed districts. Christians went from being underrepresented to being semi-effectively represented. The electoral system ensured better cooperation among the groups, but it did not satisfy all of them. Due to the dissatisfaction of both Shias and Christians, negotiations on a new electoral system continued until 2017 when Lebanon adopted the PR open list system in 15 districts.

In May 2018, Lebanon implemented the PR system for the first time after years of political

negotiations. Observing the 2018 and 2022 parliamentary elections, we can conclude that the PR system enhanced the representation of different groups in society, especially political and confessional minorities. It also affected the voting behavior and the electoral dynamics in various districts, by boosting participation, promoting cooperation among parties, and reducing confessional conflicts. Minority groups who did not vote before because their vote was meaningless under the majoritarian system, were motivated to vote again. The different shapes of the electoral districts, including confessional homogeneous, and mixed districts, created a balance between electoral competition within each confession and cooperation among confessions. The PR system, especially in mixed districts, made most parties cooperate to secure the electoral quotient, which lowered the intensity of confessional rhetoric, as cooperation overcame confessional mobilization.

The historical correlation between internal conflicts and electoral representation in Lebanon provides valuable insights into the country's political dynamics. The evolution of the electoral system, driven by the need to address conflicts and ensure fair representation, reflects Lebanon's complex socio-political landscape. Despite the challenges, the country has made significant strides towards achieving effective representation and cooperation among the confessions. In conclusion, while no electoral system can serve as a panacea for the shortcomings of any country's political system, the most suitable system is one that ensures accurate and effective group representation and simultaneously fosters spaces for inter-group cooperation. The more an electoral system aligns with these two objectives, the more reassured societal components feel about their existence and active participation in the political system, and the

more inter-group cooperation is bolstered. ♦

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